

1B: COA Development Tool for Avery

Condition	Narrative Description	Stimulus Classes	Potentially Aversive Stimuli Included?	Materials and Implementers
A	Avery does not have access to attention or tangible items. He is not expected to work.	N/A		
B	Avery has free access to attention from the preferred RBT.	Attention		High-preferred RBT
C	Avery has free access to attention from the non-preferred RBT.	Attention	Yes	Non-preferred RBT
D	Avery is required to complete chore-like demands such as folding laundry, arranging shoes, and cleaning windows.		Yes	Chore demands
E	Avery can play games with a preferred RBT, but the RBT arranges it such that Avery is denied winning the game often.	Tangible, Attention	Yes	High-preferred tangibles High-preferred RBT
F	Avery has free access to the caregiver's attention.	Attention		Caregiver
G	Avery has free access to the RBT's attention and has free access to tangible items.	Attention Tangible		High-preferred tangibles High-preferred RBT
H	Avery has free access to preferred tangible items.	Tangible		